

Report on preliminary identification of relevant omics data

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Project summary:

The **S2TOX** - “*Mechanistic Assessment of Cardiotoxicity using Integrated In Silico and In Vitro Modeling*” project is an interdisciplinary initiative designed to replace traditional animal testing with a human-relevant, *in vitro-in silico* platform for evaluating drug-induced cardiotoxicity (DICT). Using anthracyclines as a primary case study, the project aims to mechanistically explain and predict how cardiac damage varies according to a patient’s sex and age.

S2TOX is structured into four Work Packages (WP):

- WP1 (*in silico* modeling): Optimizing an Adverse Outcome Pathway (AOP) network and building a probabilistic Boolean model parameterized with human transcriptomics data.
- WP2 (*in vitro* testing): Establishing a human iPSC-derived cardiac organoid platform to generate functional and omics data for model calibration.
- WP3 (validation & trials): Validating the model against the organoid data and conducting virtual clinical trials to profile toxicity mechanisms across different patient profiles.
- WP4 (management & training): Open science dissemination, data management, and professional development.

Omics data collection for WP1

Anthracycline-induced cardiotoxicity data from the HeCaToS consortium

Background

Anthracyclines (e.g., **doxorubicin**, **epirubicin**, **idarubicin**, **daunorubicin**) are important chemotherapies with a recognized risk of cardiotoxicity that can progress to reduced left-ventricular ejection fraction and heart failure. The **HeCaToS project** (*Human Exposure-causing Adverse effects on Tissues and Organs*) generated multi-omics datasets in human 3D induced pluripotent stem cell (iPSC)-derived cardiac microtissues under physiologically based pharmacokinetic (PBPK)-informed, repeated dosing, plus human cardiac biopsies from female and male patients with ages varying from 31 to 87 years (average 62 years). In the *in vitro* setting, for each compound, two dosing profiles (therapeutic vs. toxic) and seven time points (therapeutic: 2–8–24–72–168–240–336 h; toxic: 0–2–8–24–72–168–240 h) with three replicates per time point were measured across RNA sequencing (RNA-seq), proteomics (liquid chromatography–tandem mass spectrometry - LC-MS/MS), epigenomics (MeDIP-seq), metabolomics (LC-MS and nuclear magnetic resonance - NMR), and functional endpoints (adenosine triphosphate (ATP), caspase-3/7, oxygen consumption). PBPK models and dosing files are archived in BioStudies and openly available for the scientific community for reuse and further exploration (M. Verheijen et al., 2022).

Regarding S2TOX, the relevant datasets comprise RNA-seq, proteomics, and functional data. Below, I provide a context analysis of the datasets present among the HeCaToS data that can serve to the goals of S2TOX.

- All data described here is available at BioStudies (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/>) in an open access and open source manner.

In vitro (cardiac microtissues; anthracyclines and controls)

Design: Repeated-dose, PBPK-informed regimens for doxorubicin, epirubicin, idarubicin, daunorubicin and other pharmaceutical compounds; pooled microtissues per sample; three replicates per time point.

Molecular endpoints were measured via transcriptomics and proteomics: RNA-seq for gene-level counts and miRNA-seq for microRNAs, and label-free LC-MS/MS with protein groups and peptide-spectrum matches tracked across time points. **Functional endpoints** included ATP content quantified by the CellTiter-Glo luminescence assay as a proxy for viable cell number, caspase 3 and 7 activity as an apoptosis readout, and oxygen consumption assessed by extracellular O₂ measurements using MitoXpress® Xtra. Oxygen consumption was profiled acutely over 2 h and, for doxorubicin exposure, longitudinally over 7 days.

Table 1 describes the compounds and RNA-seq, proteomics and functional data accession numbers in BioStudies (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/>), while **Table 2** describes the same information for the negative control scenarios.

Table 1. HeCaToS cardiac anthracycline datasets (*in vitro*)

Cardiotoxic compound	RNA-seq accession number	Proteomics accession number	Functional data accession number
Doxorubicin	S-HECA10	S-HECA2 S-HECA3	S-HECA29 S-HECA30
Epirubicin	S-HECA11	S-HECA21 S-HECA22	S-HECA25 S-HECA31
Idarubicin	S-HECA12	S-HECA352 S-HECA353	S-HECA4 S-HECA26
Daunorubicin	S-HECA148	S-HECA38 S-HECA39	NA

Table 2. Negative controls (*in vitro*)

Cardiac control	RNA-seq accession number	Proteomics accession number	Functional data accession number
DMSO (vehicle) 0.1%	S-HECA9 S-HECA46 S-HECA151	S-HECA1 S-HECA24 S-HECA54	S-HECA32
Untreated	S-HECA139	S-HECA18	NA

Human cardiac biopsies

Cohort: Non-ischaemic cardiomyopathy with decreased left-ventricular ejection fraction (LVEF); diagnostic work-up excluded significant coronary disease and primary valve disease; patients stratified into dilated cardiomyopathy (DCM) and non-dilated cardiomyopathy (NDCM) using echocardiographic criteria. Case-control matching (gender/BMI/LVEF); batch-3 excluded for transcriptomics homogeneity; final DE analysis on batches 1–2 (n=19; anthracycline-treated n=9 vs. controls n=8; in addition to 2 cancer patients without anthracyclines).

Key observations relevant to model calibration. Biopsies carry a modest DEG signal (clinical heterogeneity and long post-therapy intervals), yet exhibit overlap in long non-coding RNAs (e.g., H19, RMRP, BDNF-AS, SNHG7) with *in vitro* anthracycline responses; protein markers (e.g., LAMC1, ACTN2, TNNI1) show time-dependent *in vitro* changes and LVEF correlations *in vivo*.

Demographics.

Gender: 37 female, 14 male.

Age: median 64 years (range 31–87, n=51).

Anthropometrics: BMI median 26 kg/m² (range 20–44, n=51).

Cancer types:

Most controls list no active cancer. Among cases, the dominant diagnosis is breast cancer. Other recorded conditions include Hodgkin lymphoma, non-Hodgkin lymphoma, chronic lymphatic leukemia, uterine adenocarcinoma, larynx carcinoma, stomach cancer, neuroendocrine tumour, prostate cancer, and lymphogenic spread melanoma.

Inflammation (biopsy):

Binary pathology field indicates Yes in 14, No in 33, NA in 4. The quantitative inflammatory cell density (CD45+CD68 per mm²) is available per patient.

Genetic findings:

Genetic/molecular notes are heterogeneous: entries range from “None” and “Unknown” to specific calls and VUS (variants of unknown significance). Examples present in the table include SCN5A (pathogenic); TTN (VUS/likely pathogenic); MYHA-7 (pathogenic/likely pathogenic); MYHA-6 (VUS); RBM20/TMEM43 (VUS); DSP-gen (VUS); EMD (VUS); MyBPC3 and LaminAC (VUS); and Incomplete (negative). Use with caution—these are as reported in the sheet without harmonisation.

Table 3. Patient specimens

Patient specimen	RNA-seq accession number	Proteomics accession number	Functional data accession number
Cardiac biopsies (non-ischemic cardiomyopathy with/without prior anthracycline exposure)	S-HECA469	S-HECA27 S-HECA35	NA

How these data are relevant to S2TOX

DEGs and enrichment for KEs and AOP expansion:

Longitudinal differentially expressed genes (DEGs) derived from the HeCaToS RNA-seq can be analyzed to identify coherent biological activities (e.g., mitochondrial dysfunction/oxidative phosphorylation shifts, sarcomere remodeling, and extracellular matrix remodeling) that are repeatedly engaged across anthracyclines. These activities map naturally to key events in AOP-Wiki and to the

AOP network and support proposing new KEs and key-event relationships where gaps exist. In addition, it strengthens the biological plausibility, evidence levels and quantitative understanding of what is already reported in AOP-Wiki. The finding that time-resolved modules inferred *in vitro* also appear in human biopsies (both at the RNA and protein level) supports KE plausibility and translational relevance (Nguyen et al., 2022; Selevsek et al., 2020).

Parameterization of the probabilistic Boolean model:

HeCaToS gives both functional endpoints (ATP, oxygen consumption, caspase-3/7) and molecular profiles (RNA-seq/proteomics) across dose, time and different patient profiles (age and gender). After normalization of DEG evidence and weighting nodes by multi-omics corroboration (RNA+protein) and proximity to observable KE outcomes, data can be used for parameterization of the probabilistic Boolean model. The published biophysical mitochondrion model that reproduces ATP and membrane-potential responses under doxorubicin offers a high-fidelity submodule to anchor energy/ROS nodes and reference values for Boolean parameter ranges (Selevsek et al., 2020).

Role of human biopsy metadata:

The per-patient table (sex, age, body mass index, cancer type, chemotherapies, inflammation status, genetic findings) with cohort-level RNA-seq (S-HECA469) and proteomics (S-HECA27; S-HECA35) offers a potential **translational constraint** to S2TOX:

- It enables case–control contrasts aligned with the AOP key events and sensitivity analyses by compound or biological context (e.g., inflammation).
- It provides covariates (age, sex, and body mass index) to control confounding when validating *in vitro*-derived modules *in vivo*.
- Reported genetic findings (e.g., pathogenic SCN5A; variants of unknown significance in TTN, MYH7, RBM20, and TMEM43) suggest stratified checks where sarcomere/electrophysiology nodes are predicted to shift, improving the biological realism of the model's parameter distributions (Nguyen et al., 2022).

Next-steps

Screen transcriptomics databases for publicly available data related to cardiotoxicity.

- Gene Expression Omnibus - <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/>
- Expression Atlas - <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/gxa/home>
- Array Express - <https://harmonisation/biostudies/arrayexpress>
- BioStudies - <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/biostudies/>

Data treatment, cleaning, and harmonization using our in-house pipeline (Lesage et al., 2022) and R-ODAF (Verheijen et al., 2022). Then, these omics and functional data from other studies can be used to complete S2TOX tasks.

References

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